

Assessing Allergen Sensitization Patterns in Allergic Rhinitis Patients

V. Manoj Narayan^{1*}, M. Murugan¹, J Preena Jane², Stevenson S³

¹Department of Organon of Medicine, Sarada Krishna Homoeopathic Medical College (Affiliated to The Tamil Nadu Dr.M.G.R. Medical University, Chennai), Kulasekharam, Kanniyakumari District, Tamil Nadu, India – 629 161

²Department of Community Medicine, Sri Sairam Homoeopathy Medical College and Research Center, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India – 600044.

³Department of Homoeopathic Philosophy and Organon of Medicine, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Homoeopathic Medical College, Pune, India. 411046.

This work is a part of Ph.D. Thesis of The Tamilnadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University, Chennai

(Received: 07 October 2023

Revised: 12 November

Accepted: 06 December)

KEYWORDS

Allergic rhinitis,
Epidemiology,
Sensitization,
Triggers.

ABSTRACT

This research aims to provide insights into the diverse allergenic triggers that contribute to the development and exacerbation of allergic rhinitis, shedding light on the significance of personalized approaches to diagnosis and management. The study begins by delving into the epidemiology of allergic rhinitis, highlighting its increasing prevalence worldwide and the associated healthcare burden. Subsequently, it elucidates the various allergens that are commonly implicated in the development of allergic rhinitis, encompassing both indoor and outdoor allergens, including pollen, dust mites, animal dander, and mold spores. Furthermore, this review systematically examines the methodologies employed in assessing allergen sensitization patterns, encompassing skin prick tests, specific IgE measurements, and molecular diagnostic techniques. It discusses the advantages and limitations of each approach and emphasizes the importance of accurate and individualized allergen profiling in clinical practice. The review concludes by advocating for a holistic and patient-centered approach to managing allergic rhinitis, incorporating precise allergen sensitization assessment into clinical decision-making. It underscores the potential benefits of allergen avoidance, immunotherapy, and pharmacological interventions tailored to an individual's sensitization profile.

INTRODUCTION:

Allergic rhinitis, a prevalent chronic respiratory disorder, affects a substantial portion of the global population, leading to a significant burden on healthcare systems and the overall quality of life for affected individuals. This condition is characterized by inflammation of the nasal mucosa resulting from the immune system's exaggerated response to otherwise harmless environmental allergens. It manifests as a constellation of symptoms, including nasal congestion, sneezing, rhinorrhea, and itching of the nose and eyes.¹

The impact of allergic rhinitis extends beyond mere discomfort, as it frequently coexists with other allergic conditions, such as asthma, conjunctivitis, and atopic dermatitis. Moreover, allergic rhinitis has been associated with impaired cognitive function, sleep disturbances, and reduced work and school productivity. These factors underscore the importance of a comprehensive understanding of the condition's underlying allergen

sensitization patterns to guide effective management strategies.

Over recent decades, there has been a steady rise in the prevalence of allergic rhinitis across the globe, making it a public health concern of substantial magnitude. The factors contributing to this upward trend are multifactorial, encompassing genetic predisposition, environmental changes, urbanization, and lifestyle alterations. As a result, allergic rhinitis has emerged as a complex and dynamic health issue that demands a nuanced approach.²

This review article aims to explore and assess the allergen sensitization patterns in allergic rhinitis patients comprehensively. By delving into the specific allergens responsible for inducing allergic rhinitis, we aim to shed light on the diverse factors influencing its development. This understanding is pivotal for tailoring effective preventive measures, diagnostics, and therapeutic interventions to the distinct needs of individuals suffering from this condition.

In this comprehensive review, we will synthesize and analyze existing research, highlighting the most common allergens implicated in allergic rhinitis, regional variations in allergen sensitization, diagnostic methods for assessing sensitization patterns, and potential therapeutic strategies. The insights derived from this exploration will provide valuable guidance for healthcare professionals, researchers, and policymakers in their efforts to address the increasing prevalence of allergic rhinitis and improve the quality of life for affected individuals.

According to the Phase III International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC), the prevalence of AR varied between 0.8 to 14.9% in 6-7 years old and 1.4 to 39.7% in 13-14 years old worldwide. In Asia, this disease affects a large population, ranging from 27% in South Korea to 32% in the United Arab Emirates.³

AR is not properly diagnosed, a proper estimate of the severity of the problem has not been made and if at all diagnosed no adequate treatment is given.⁴ Earlier allergic rhinitis was deemed to be a pure local diseases nose and the nasal passages being the main part being affected. Further study indicated that the whole airway may be involved in the process.⁵

The studies on diagnosis of allergic rhinitis have been very less considering the presence of allergic rhinitis in the community and its effect on the economical aspect in the community. The diagnosis was made purely based on the medical history. The diagnosis was sufficiently accurate only for grass pollens. More tests were required for the identification of the presence of allergic rhinitis.⁶

The family doctors also known as primary care physicians or general practitioners play a major part in dealing with the diagnosis, treatment given, and the information gathered and monitoring of the above patients. In all these cases we lack the evidence-based approach to treatment. The guidelines for such an evidence-based approach to disease is often lacking in the primary care set up.⁷

The epidemiological studies often show marked difference between the presence of allergic rhinitis symptoms and the allergy tests conducted. These results are found to vary worldwide. The allergy tests were found to be positive without the symptoms pointing to allergic rhinitis.⁸

Allergic rhinitis diagnosis is often made on a clinical basis depending on the history and physical examination. A proper diagnosis is possible only with either testing for allergen-specific IgE or allergy skin testing.⁹

There are other tools which include nasal provocation testing, nasal cytology (e.g., blown secretions, scraping, lavage, biopsy), nasolaryngoscopy, and intradermal skin testing. WHO limits the use of these diagnostic

procedures due to the fact that it is only used by the researchers and these tests do not play a great role in the routine practices.¹⁰

Interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) plays a great part in the process of allergic diseases. The studies have shown the relation of it in allergen-induced inflammation. Many studies have shown that levels of IL-1 β level were significantly higher in allergic disorders. The blockage of the pathway of IL-1 β could result in reduction of inflammation. IL-1 β could be a potential biomarker of AR. But the role and mechanism of IL-1 β in AR has not been fully understood. There has been difficulties in proper collection of samples. This has led to a limited use of IL-1 β as a clinical diagnosis and treatment marker for AR.¹¹

Atopy could be decided by evaluating total IgE and eosinophil levels. Total IgE and eosinophil values are helpful indices for the proper evaluation of the diagnosis and the follow-up. These tests are helpful where the facilities are less to come to an understanding of the presence of atopic illness.¹²

The study of the effectiveness of nasal smear for eosinophils. Its less invasive and easily available. Only in severe eosinophilia it was found that the nasal and blood eosinophils levels were found to be increased and a correlation could be made.¹³

Nasal inspection provides an overview and be performed through anterior rhinoscopy or at least by an otoscope. There will be secretions usually watery secretions in allergic rhinitis. Nasal endoscopy helps to exclude anatomical abnormalities or inflammatory conditions other than allergy (ie, chronic rhinosinusitis with or without nasal polyps).¹⁴

A combination of medical history with either RASTs or SPTs resulted in a proper diagnosis who is allergic who is not allergic. SPTs did not perform better than RASTs. RAST criteria performance being better is due to introduction of the CAP system since the sensitivity is much greater than the paper disk method. Skin prick test is effective method in the hands of an experienced physician. In SPT we will have to suspend medications and there is a lack of reliability in cases of eczema patients. The use of both RASTs or SPTs in combination did not become clinically relevant.¹⁵

SPT, allergen sIgE, ELR: Eosinophil-to-lymphocyte ratio, and ENR: Eosinophil-to-neutrophil ratio be used to diagnose AR in adult patients. Increased serum total IgE levels in patients with AR may be compared with patients with NAR which will help in the differential diagnosis. More studies are necessary to investigate inflammatory markers like ELR, ENR, and NLR that can be measured

with the help of a complete blood count and nasal cytology.¹⁶

The evaluation of nasal Nitric Oxide has shown potential as a useful biomarker in AR. Its levels increase in allergic rhinitis and with treatment it was found to be decreased. The problem in its usage is establishment of a standardized method for sampling, analyzing, and reporting of the nasal Nitric Oxide measurements. We still need further understanding of the usefulness of this biomarker in the monitoring of Th2 inflammation and treatments across different clinical environments like community, hospital, and rehabilitation settings. Most importantly reliable cut-off values have to be established and a standardized procedure for nNO assessment has to be brought out to be useful in the diagnosis and evaluation of testaments.¹⁷

It is necessary to have an accurate and sustainable biomarkers/predictor of response. A proper identification of biomarkers will help to create a more personalized approach.¹⁸ Homoeopathy is a system of percolated medicine which caters to each individual who is suffering from the disease. Homoeopathy is more concerned with the patient who is suffering with the disease rather than the disease itself¹⁹. A proper biomarker will help to provide proper evidence of the efficacy of the treatment.

This work is a part of Ph.D. Thesis of The Tamilnadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University, Chennai

REFERENCES

- Meng Y, Wang C, Zhang L. Recent developments and highlights in allergic rhinitis. *Allergy*. 2019;74:2320–2328.
- _____
- Nur Husna SM, Tan HTT, Md Shukri N, Mohd Ashari NS and Wong KK (2022) Allergic Rhinitis: A Clinical and Pathophysiological Overview. *Front. Med.* 9:874114.
- Chong SN, Chew FT. Epidemiology of allergic rhinitis and associated risk factors in Asia. *World allergy organization journal*. 2018;11:17.
- Hellings PW, Scadding G, Bachert C, Bjermer L, Canonica GW, Cardell LO, Carney AS, Constantinidis J, Deneyer L, Diamant Z, Durham S, Gevaert P, Harvey R, Hopkins C, Kjeldsen A, Klimek L, Lund VJ, Price D, Rimmer J, Ryan D, Roberts G, Sahlstrand-Johnson P, Salmi S, Samji M, Scadding G, Smith P, Steinsvik A, Wagenmann M, Seys S, Wahn U, Fokkens WJ. EUFORIA treatment algorithm for allergic rhinitis. *Rhinology*. 2020 Dec 1;58(6):618-622. doi: 10.4193/Rhin20.376. PMID: 32991658.
- Small and Kim: Allergic rhinitis. *Allergy, Asthma & Clinical Immunology* 2011 7(Suppl 1):S3.
- Marcel Jjs Crobach, Jo Hermans, Adrian A Kaptein, Jacobus Ridderikhoff, Hans Petri, Jan D Mulder (1998) The diagnosis of allergic rhinitis: how to combine the medical history with the results of radioallergosorbent tests and skin prick tests, *Scandinavian Journal of Primary Health Care*, 16:1, 30-36, DOI: [10.1080/028134398750003377](https://doi.org/10.1080/028134398750003377)
- Bousquet J, Reid JS, C. van Weel, Baena E, Giorgio Walter Canonica, Pascal Demoly, et al. Allergic rhinitis management pocket reference 2008. *Allergy*. 2008 Aug 1;63(8):990–6.
- Mims, JW. Epidemiology of allergic rhinitis. *Int Forum Allergy Rhinol*. 2014; 4: S18–S20.
- Akhouri S, House SA. Allergic Rhinitis. [Updated 2023 Jul 16]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK538186/>
- Quillen DM, Feller DB. Diagnosing rhinitis: allergic vs. nonallergic. *Am Fam Physician*. 2006 May 1;73(9):1583-90. PMID: 16719251.
- Wang HR, Wei SZ, Song XY, Wang Y, Zhang WB, Ren C, et al. IL-1 β and Allergy: Focusing on Its Role in Allergic Rhinitis. *Mediators of Inflammation*. 2023 Apr 12;2023:1–11.
- Saglam NO, Ozkars MY, Altas U, Altas ZM. Evaluation of the predictive value of total IgE and absolute eosinophil levels on allergy test positivity. *Age (years)*. 2023;5:0-17.
- Priyadarshinee A, Khadka S, Regmi S. Role of Nasal Smear for Eosinophils in Patients of Allergic Rhinitis. *Journal of KIST Medical College*. 2023 May 19;5(9).
- Tenero L, Vaia R, Ferrante G, Maule M, Venditto L, Piacentini G, Senna G, Caminati M. Diagnosis and Management of Allergic Rhinitis in Asthmatic Children. *Journal of asthma and allergy*. 2023 Dec 31:45-57.
- Crobach MJ, Hermans JO, Kaptein AA, Ridderikhoff J, Petri H, Mulder JD. The diagnosis of allergic rhinitis: how to combine the medical history with the results of radioallergosorbent tests and skin prick tests. *Scandinavian journal of primary health care*. 1998 Jan 1;16(1):30-6.
- Selçuk A, Keren M. The evaluation of eosinophil-to-lymphocyte, eosinophil-to-neutrophil, and neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratios in adults with

- allergic/non-allergic rhinitis. *Gulhane Medical Journal*. 2023 Mar 1;65(1).
17. Marcuccio G, Ambrosino P, Merola C, Manzo F, Motta A, Rea G, Cantone E, Maniscalco M. Clinical Applications of Nasal Nitric Oxide in Allergic Rhinitis: A Review of the Literature. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2023 Aug 2;12(15):5081.
 18. Tenero L, Vaia R, Ferrante G, Maule M, Venditto L, Piacentini G, Senna G, Caminati M. Diagnosis and Management of Allergic Rhinitis in Asthmatic Children. *Journal of asthma and allergy*. 2023 Dec 31:45-57.
 19. C. Sherin Sheeba, R.M. Nithin, T.S. Asta Eshwaran, Anjaly R Nair, T. Ajayan, N.V. Sugathan. Estimation Of Serum IgE in Allergic Rhinitis Pre and Post Homoeopathic Treatment. *Eur. Chem. Bull.* 2022, 11(Regular Issue 12), 710 –713.
 20. Sheeba CS, Nithin RM, Eshwaran TA, Nair AR, Ajayan T, Sugathan NV. ESTIMATION OF SERUM IGE IN ALLERGIC RHINITIS PRE AND POST HOMOEOPATHIC TREATMENT.